

Formulation And Evaluation Of Harbal Hand Wash By Using Natural Ingredients By Simple Method

Akash Wankhede^{1*}, Akshay Ghule², Amol Jadhav³, Priya Dandekar⁴

^{1*} M. Pharm Scholar, Gawande College of Pharmacy, Sakharkherda, Buldhana, Maharashtra-443202

^{2,4} Assistant Professor, Gawande College of Pharmacy, Sakharkherda, Buldhana, Maharashtra-443202

³ Principal, Gawande College of Pharmacy, Sakharkherda, Buldhana, Maharashtra-443202.

ABSTRACT

The perfume of the herbal hand wash keeps the skin fresh and lithe. The mild foaming action does not cause any irritation while using herbal hand wash. It also helps to remove the dirt and oil effectively from the skin. It also helps to clear antiseptic and fungal problems faced by the skin. Removing germs through handwashing therefore helps prevent diarrhea and respiratory infections and may even help prevent skin and eye infections. Handmade herbal soaps have therapeutic benefits in addition. Those with sensitive skin or conditions such as psoriasis or eczema can take aid from natural handmade soaps. Glycerin soap also protects the skin which is sensitive and delicate, and when herbal soaps are used, you can be sure that the glycerin content is high absorbing water in the air and ensuring the skin remains soft and healthy. Handwashing removes visible dirt from hands and reduces the number of harmful microorganisms such as E. Coli and S aureus can be carried by people, food, animal or equipment & transmitted. To protect the skin from harmful microorganism and to avoid spreading of numerous contagious diseases, hand washing is extremely important. Books on ayurvedic medicine, written in the vedic period (3500–1600 B.C.) describe practices, including the use of medicinal plants. In modern complementary and alternative medical practice, plants are the primary source of therapeutics because bioactive components present in each part of the plant, including the seeds, root, stem, leaves, and fruit. The benefits associated with the use of medicinal plants are like they are cost-effectiveness and global availability. They safe as compare to synthetic compound. They are natural product so they are side effect free which is most important advantage of medicinal plant. Skin is first protection line of human body it covered the inner part of body and protect them protection from the pathogens. so, protect the skin from harmful microbes and to prevent spreading of many contagious diseases hand washing is important precaution. Hands are primary mode of transmission of microbes and infection.

Keywords: Perfumes, soaps.

INTRODUCTION

When only surfactants in combination with non-aggressive solvent cleansers are used in the cleansing compositions, the cleaning power of the composition may be inadequate when stubborn or embedded oils are present. If the chemical formula is too aggressive in terms of its solubilizing or emulsifying power, skin can be harmed due to defatting of the dermal oils thereof, particularly when the cleanser is used repeatedly. The importance of handwashing for human health – particularly for people in vulnerable Circumstances like mothers who had just given birth

or wounded soldiers sin hospitals – was first Recognized in mid 19th century by two pioneers of hand hygiene. At that time most people still Believed that infections were caused by foul odors called miasmas. In the 1980s, foodborne outbreaks and healthcare-associated infections led United States Centers for Disease Control and Prevention to more actively promote hand hygiene as an Important way to prevent the spread of infection.

The outbreak of swine flu in 2009 led to increased awareness in many countries of importance Of washing hands with soap to protect oneself from such

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infectious diseases. For example, Posters with “correct hand washing techniques” were hung up next to hand washing sinks in Public toilets and in toilets of office buildings and airports in Germany(1). Industrial and hand cleansing formulations typically contain a surfactant that solubilizes or Emulsifies the oils, debris, and soil present on a substrate. These formulations inherently have Oil-cleansing limitations when oil-emulsifiability or solvency alone is used as a cleaning Mechanism. When only surfactants in combination with non-aggressive solvent cleansers are used in the Cleansing compositions, the cleaning power of the composition may be inadequate when Stubborn or embedded oils are present. If the chemical formula is too aggressive in terms of its Solubilizing or emulsifying power, skin can be harmed due to defatting of the dermal oils thereof, Particularly when the cleanser is used repeatedly.

Hygiene:

It is basically defined as branch of science which is involved in knowledge and practices related to promotion of health. Spread of infections (bacterial and viral) can be prevented by following hygiene practices. Since cleaning processes (e.g hand washing, taking bath) removes dirt and soil as well as infectious microbes they are commonly used to achieve hygiene. Hygiene is defined as maintenance of cleanliness practices which carries utmost importance in maintenance of health keeping bodily hygiene and usage of cleansers are requisites of healthy living. These concepts highlight the need of maintaining hygiene in prevention of diseases.(2)

Hand Hygiene:

The act of cleaning hands with water or soap or liquid is generally referred to as hand hygiene. The importance of washing hands is that it cleanses the hands of harmful chemicals and Pathogens (bacteria and virus). Hand hygiene is especially important for people working in medical field and restaurants or who cook and serve food to general public. Proper hand hygiene can decrease the transmission of cold viruses and other germ is an established fact. Washing Hands is considered the best way to maintain personal hygiene and protect oneself from diseases. promotion and implementation of hand washing program in the

schools, brought a reduction of 42% in school absenteeism and reduced the incidence of gastrointestinal and respiratory illness among children handwashing It refers to washing hands with plain or antimicrobial soap or water. In actual practice, it can vary considerably from a brief rinse of hands to extensive scrubbing. The purpose of hand washing in the health care setting is to remove pathogenic microorganisms (“germs”) and avoid transmitting them. It has been reported that lack of handwashing remains at unacceptable levels in most medical environments, with large numbers of Doctors and nurses routinely forgetting to wash their hands before touching patients. One study showed that proper hand washing and other simple procedures can decrease the rate of catheterrelated bloodstream infections by 66 percent. Skin is one of the most exposed part of the body requires protection from the pathogens. To protect the skin from harmful microorganisms and to prevent spreading of many contagious diseases hand washing is absolutely an important precaution. correct use of a fingernail brush to wash hands and fingertips is the best way to assure removal of transien microorganisms.

Six steps to effective hand washing

Step No 1: Wet hand apply soap. Rub palm together until soap is bubbly.

Fig no.1: Step 1 in effective handwashing

Step no 2 :Rub each palm over the back of the other hand

Fig.no2:Step 2 in effective handwashing

Step No 3:Rubs between your fingers on each hand.

Fig.no3: Step 3 in effective handwashing

Step no 4:Rub your hands with the fingers together.

Fig.no4:Step 4 in effective handwashing

Step no 5:Rub around each of your thumbs.

Fig.no5: Step 5 in effective handwashing

Step no 6:Rub in circles on your palms. Then rinse and dry your hands.

Fig no.6: Step 6 in effective handwashing

Advantages of Herbal Hand wash (3)

1. No side effects.
2. Bacteria on our hands can be minimized.
3. It also helps to clear antiseptic and fungal problem faced by the skin.
4. It also helps to remove dirt and oil effectively from the skin
5. Easier access compared to using soap and water.
6. The easiest way to get rid of microorganism.
7. Hand wash prevent germs from entering into our body.

Disadvantages of herbal Hand wash

1. Herbal cosmetics have slower effects as compare to the allopathic dosage forms.
2. Also, it requires long term therapy.
3. They are difficult to mask taste and odor.
4. Manufacturing process is time consuming and complicated

Market preparation [5]

1. Godrej magic hand wash
2. Patanjali antibacterial herbal hand wash
3. Medimix herbal hand wash
4. Srisri cleanup hand wash
5. Tarushi hand wash
6. Axiom herbal hand wash
7. Hadoo herbal hand wash
8. Care life herbal hand wash
9. Eclin antibacterial herbal hand wash
10. Fresco antibacterial herbal hand wash

PLANT/DRUG PROFILE:**1)Tulsi****Fig.no.7:Tulsi plant****Scientific classification of tulsi:**

Kingdom : plantae

Division : magnoliophyta

Class : Magnoliopsida

Order : Lameness

Genus: : Ocimum

Species : O.tonuiiflorum

Bionomical name : ocimum tenuifloram/Ocimum sanctum

Ocimum sanctum commonly known as holy basil or Tulsi. Tulsi consist of fresh And dried leaves of ocimum sanctum belonging to family Lamiaceae. Tulsi is an aromatic Perennial plant.tulsi known for its detoxifying purifying and antimicrobial properties.tulsi Helps to protect your hands by killing 99.99%of germs.Tulsi now,days cultivated Commercially for its volatile oil.it is much branched small herb 30 to 75cm in height. All Parts of tulsi are used in medicine especially fresh and dried leaves.leaves are ablong acute With entire sterolate margins pubscnt on both sides and minutely gland dotted. The leavesAre green in colour with aromatic flavors and slightly compressed. Seeds are reddish black And subglobose. The leaf is dorsiventral stomach are of dicyclic type. Particularly abundant On lower surface.(8,9)

Chemical constituents:-

It contains approximately 70%Eugenia,carvacrol 3% and Eugene methyl Ether(20).It also contains caryophyllin,seeds contain fixed oil with good drying properties. The plant also contain alkaloids,glycosides,sapping,tannis an appreciable amount of Vitamin c and traces of maleic and Tartaric acids.the fresh leaves,it's juice and volatile oil are used for various purposes.

Uses of Tulsi:-

The leaves are used as stimulants, aromatic, spasmolytic, diaphoretic The Juice is used as an

antiperiodic and act as constituents of several preparation for skin disease

2) Neem:

Fig.no-8:Neem Plant

- Scientific classification of Neem:-
- Kingdom: - Plantae
- Order: - saphinadales
- Family: -Meliaceae
- Genius: -Azadirachta
- Species: -A.Indica
- Bionomical name: - Azadirachta Indica

Products made from neem trees have been used in the traditional medicine of India for Centuries, but there is insufficient clinical evidence to indicate any benefits of using neem for medicinal purposes.] In adults, no specific doses have been established, and short-term use of neem appears to be safe, while long term use may harm the kidneys or liver; in small children, neem oil is toxic and can lead to death. Neem may also cause Miscarriages, infertility, and low blood sugar. Neem is a key ingredient in non-pesticidal management (NPM), providing a natural alternative to synthetic pesticides. Neem seeds are ground into powder that is soaked overnight In water and sprayed on the crop. To be effective,it must be applied repeatedly, at least every ten days

.Neem does not directly kill insects. It acts as an anti-feedant , repellent, and egg-laying deterrent and thus protects The crop from damage. The insects starve

and die within a few days. Neem also suppresses the subsequent hatching Of their eggs. Neem-based fertilizers have been effective against southern armyworm. Neem cake may be used as fertilizer citation needed. Neem oil has been shown to avert termite attack as an ecofriendly and economical Agent.

Azadirachta is a genus of two species of trees in the family Meliaceae. Numerous species have been proposed For the genus but only two are currently recognized, Azadirachta excelsa and the economically important tree Azadirachta Indica, the Neem tree, from which neem oil is extracted. Both species are native to the Indomalaysian region, and A. Indica is also widely cultivated and naturalized outside its native range.

Chemical constituents:-

The chemical constituents are found in the leaves of name as nimbin, nimbanene, 6desacetylnimbinene, Nimbandiol, nimbolide, ascorbic acid, nhexacosanol and amino acid, 7desacetyl-7-benzoylazadiradione, 7 Desacetyl-7-benzoylgedunin, 17-hydroxyazadiradione and nimbiol.

Neem has been recommended for skin care:

- 1)Treating acne and hyperpigmentation
- 2)Healing burns and abrasions
- 3) Moisturizing the skin
- 4)Relieving dandruff
- 5)Stimulating hair growth

3) Aloe vera:

Fig.no-9: Aloe vera Plant

Scientific classification of aloe-vera:-

Kingdom : plantae

Order : Aspargels

Family : Xanthorrhoeaceae

Genus : Aloe

Species : A.Vera

Bionomical name : Aloe vera

Aloevera is a succulent plant Species that probably originated in northern Africa. The Species does not have any naturally occurring population, although closely related Aloe Does not occur in northern Africa. The Species is frequently cited as being used in herbal Medicine since the beginning of the first century. Extract from the Aloe vera widely used In cosmetic and alternative medicine industries, being marketed as variously having Regenerating, healing ,or smoothing properties.

Aloe is the dried juice collected by incision from the basis of the leaves of various Species Of aloe. Aloe perry Baker, aloevera linn, or Aloe barbandesis belonging to family Liliaceae, Aloe perry Baker is found in socotra and zanzibar Islands and in their Neighbouring areas and so the obtain from these Species is known as soothing and Zanzibar. Aloevera linn also known as vulgaris or Aloe barbendesis. aloe is an perennial Growing to 0.8by 1ml ata slow rate. The plant prefers light (sandy)and medium soil. Can Grow nutritionally poor soil. The plant prefer acid basic and neutral soil. It cannot grow in Shade it requires dry or moist soil and can tolerate drought. They are xenophobic plant .it can be propagated by seeds. seeds are shown in the spring in warm green house.

Formulation Tables:**Formulation No-1**

Sr.No	Ingredients	Quantity (gm)	Action
1	Tulsi	10	Antimicrobial agent
2	Neem	10	Anti-bacterial agent
3	Aloevera	10	Antimicrobial agent
4	Chandan	8	Fragrance

Chemical constituents:-

The most important constituents of aloevera are three isomers of Aloins ,barbaloins and isobarbaloins which constitute so called crystalline along. present In drug at from 10-30% other constituents are amorphous aloin, resin, eroding and Aloe Emodin.

Barbaloins is present in all the varieties. it is slightly yellow colour, bitter water soluble Isobarbaloin is a crystalline substance present in curaco Aloe and in trace amounts in cape Aloe and in absent in socotrine and zanzibar Aloe. The chief constituents of socotrine Aloe And zanzibar Aloe is barbaloin. (10).

MATERIAL & METHOD

Material: Neem powder, Aloevera Powder, Tulsi powder, Chandan Powder, SLS, Carbopol 940, Methyl Paraben.

Method of Preparation :

- 1) Herbal Handwash powder was prepared using Carbopol 940 as Gelling agent .
- 2) Neem, Aloevera, Tulsi powder were measured accurately and mixed properly.
- 3) Chandan is used as natural fragrance agent
- 4) Sodium lauryl sulphate is used as foaming agent and mixed in the above mixture .
- 5) The methyl paraben (solid form) is used as preservative.
- 6) All the powders and expients were properly mixed in given amount and Lastly, it was stored in well closed container and labelled suitably for further analysis [11,12].

5	SLS	4	Foaming agent
6	Carbapol 940	6	Gelling agent
7	Methyl Paraben	0.50	Preservative

Table No1: Formulation 1**Formulation No-2**

Sr.No	Ingredients	Quantity (gm)	Action
1	Tulsi	8	Antimicrobial agent
2	Neem	12	Anti-bacterial agent
3	Aloevera	10	Antimicrobial agent
4	Chandan	8	Fragrance
5	SLS	5	Foaming agent
6	Carbapol 940	6	Gelling agent
7	Methyl Paraben	0.50	Preservative

Table No2: Formulation 2**Formulation No-3**

Sr. No	Ingredients	Quantity (gm)	Action
1	Tulsi	10	Antimicrobial agent
2	Neem	9	Anti-bacterial agent
3	Aloevera	13	Antimicrobial agent
4	Chandan	8	Fragrance
5	SLS	4	Foaming agent
6	Carbapol 940	5	Gelling agent
7	Methyl Paraben	0.50	Preservative

Table No3: Formulation 3**EVALUATION PARAMETERS:-**

Prepared formulation of Herbal Hand wash Gel was subjected to following evaluation parameters:

1. Organoleptic Evaluation Parameters like colour, odour, texture was carried out Colour and texture were evaluated by visual and touch sensation respectively. The Odour was inspected by sensing the formulation[13].
2. Appearance and Homogeneity: Appearance and Homogeneity was evaluated by visual Inspection.
3. Grittiness: 1ml of Gel was taken on finger tips and rubbed between two fingertips, then the formulation was evaluated[14,15,16].
4. Skin irritation test: Skin Irritation Test was evaluated by applying Polyherbal Hand wash Gel on skin and left for 30 min, after 30 minutes of washing observe any itching, rashes or redness on skin by sensory and visual inspection.

Fig.no-10:Skin irritation test(before).

Fig.no11-Skin irritation test (after)

5)PH :Using 100ml of distilled water, 1ml of herbal hand wash sample was dissolved. Using a standardized digital pH meter, the pH of the obtained solution was assessed.[17,18].

Fig.no-12 :Ph test

6)Foam Test :A 100 ml measuring cylinder was filled with 25 ml of herbal hand wash and it was shaken ten times. The foam volume was measured at 1-minute intervals for 10 mins

Fig no.13: Cleaning action.

Fig no.14: Foam test

7) Spread ability: 0.5gm of Sample of Herbal Hand wash Gel was pressed between two slides and left for about 5 minutes where no more spreading was expected. Diameter of spreaded circle was measured in cm and was taken as comparative values for spread ability.

8) Viscosity: The viscosity of Herbal Hand wash was determined by using Ostwald viscometer[19,20,21].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The present study was carried out to formulate herbal hand wash using Neem ,Tulsi, Aloe vera & Chandan powder.

1) Organoleptic Evaluation:

Sr No	Parameter	F1	F2	F3
1	Colour	White	White	White
2	Odour	Pleasant	Pleasant	Pleasant
3	Texture	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth
4	State	Solid	Solid	Solid

Table No.4: Organoleptic Evaluation of Formulations

2) Appearance and Homogeneity:

Sr.no	Formulation	Appearance	Homogeneity
1.	F1	No Change	Homogenous
2.	F2	No Change	Homogenous
3.	F3	No Change	Homogenous

Table No.5: Appearance and Homogeneity testing of Formulations

3) Skin irritation test:

Sr No	Formulation	Irritant effect	Erythema	Edema
1	F1	Nil	Nil	Nil
2	F2	Nil	Nil	Nil
3	F3	Nil	Nil	Nil

Table No.6:Skin irritation test of Formulations

4)Ph:

Sr No	Formulation	PH
1	F1	5.2
2	F2	5.5
3	F3	5.7

Table No.7:Ph test of Formulations

6)Foam Test :

Sr.no	Formulation	Foam Height	Foam Retention
1.	F1	5 cm	3 min
2.	F2	6 cm	5 min
3.	F3	4 cm	2 min

Table No.8:Foam test of Formulations

7) Spreadability:

Sr No.	Formulation	Spreadability
1	F1	26.5 sec
2	F2	29.2 sec
3	F3	31sec

Table No.8: Spreadability test of Formulations

DISCUSSION:

Preparation and evaluation of herbal handwash was done. The physicochemical parameters of the prepared handwash were determined. The formulations exhibit good appearance characteristics as well as the pH was found in the range 5-6 which is the desired pH. Other parameters such as foam height, foam retention and high temperature stability were determined. The various parameters results are tabulated. The present work is concerned with the formulation of handwash using ethanolic extracts of Herbal drugs. The formulated handwash was stable showing no color change and good appearance and is foamy in nature. It showed good skin compatibility and causes no irritation. When tested on volunteers, the human body experienced certain adverse effects from chemically produced handwash. Comparing herbal handwash to chemical handwash, the former has less adverse effects.

SUMMARY:

The aim of the present study is to formulate and evaluate herbal hand wash gel by using extracts of *Azadirachta Indica* (neem powder), *Ocimum tenuiflorum* (Tulasi powder), *Mentha* (mint powder), *Syzygium aromaticum* (cloveOil), *Sapindus mukorossi* (rithapowder), carbopol 940 (gelling agent), methyl Paraben (preservative), Glycerin (softening agent), distilled water, (vehicle), Turmeric (colorant), Rose oil (perfume), Saponin Extract. To select the Plant materials. To extract powders from plants by air drying method to get particle free extract. To prepare herbal Hand was gel by using suitable agents. To evaluate herbal hand wash gel. Like cosmetics and cosmeceuticals (a Cosmetic that has claimed medicinal properties) are topically applied but they have ingredients that influences the Biological actions of skin. The WHO estimates that most of the population of Asian country presently use herbal Medicine for the purpose of hand hygiene includes preparation of hand wash. The present study was carried out to Formulate polyherbal hand wash gel containing herbal extract which is used not only for the purpose of cleaning Hands but also for the prevention of bacterial growth. Its composition was prepared according to skin delicateness so That it cannot cause any type of irritation. Hence it can be concluded that polyherbal hand wash gel are much better Than the plain soaps or existing marketed hand wash due to their ingredient's and effectiveness on our skin of hands As well a suitable for all type of skin.

CONCLUSION :

Literature reveals that leaves of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) possess Antimicrobial property, leaves of Tulsi possess Antibacterial activity, and extract of aloe vera possess Antibacterial activity. Hence the present study was designed to formulate polyherbal hand wash having Antimicrobial and antibacterial properties the poly herbal hand wash was found to be brown colour non greasy smooth in texture and easily washable with a good PH near to normal skin PH range .No skin irritation wash observed while using it for few days .From all the studies we can finally states that polyherbal hand wash has shown cleansing action with no skin irritation and easy to use as it is

polyherbal hand wash ,so decreases the chances of side effects.

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